

Transition in Indian E-Commerce Market due to COVID-19: A Shift From Brick and Mortar Stores to E-Commerce

Ankita Chaturvedi* and Vaishali Agrawal**

*Department of Accounting and Taxation
IIS (Deemed to be University), Jaipur, India*

Abstract: This paper analyzes how the e-commerce industry has changed in COVID-19 and what is going to be the way forward for e-commerce after COVID-19. The study is predicated on 600 Indian internet buyers across income groups and geographies accessing a good assortment of goods and services, selected on the idea of stratified sampling. The study focuses on how the shopping habits of consumers change in the near and distant future, what are the consumers' expectations from the post COVID-19 e-commerce industry. To test the objectives of the study weighted average mean, rank analysis, correlation analysis, and logistic regression have been applied. It is found that during this COVID-19 pandemic consumers have tried their best to adapt to strange times without a lot of footholds and shifting their behavior as a result.

Keywords: COVID-19, E-Commerce, Online Shopping, Preference, Consumers Expectations, Goods And Services

JEL Classification Number: C83, D10, D12, M20, M21

1. Introduction

E-commerce stands for electronic commerce that means electronic trading of goods and services. It has gained popularity in the world's economy over the period of time. Initially, it has begun in 1995 to maintain the need of companies for digital goods transactions. The things which can be sent through digital networks are called digital goods (Laudon and Laudon, 2015). E-commerce generates great business opportunities like the sale of products, revenue growth, and e-service options (Rohm and Swaminathan, 2004) especially for companies like Amazon, Flipkart because of their interactive nature, low cost, a wide range of products, etc. (Santos and Vijande et al., 2013). Nowadays, e-commerce plays a significant role in any business. In addition, based on different types of relationships, e-commerce has been categorized as Business to Business (B2B), Consumer to Business (C2B), Business to Consumer (B2C), and Consumer to consumer (C2C).

The arrival of COVID-19, which stands for Corona (CO), Virus (VI), Disease (D) in 2019 (19), occurred in Wuhan, has had a vital influence on the Indian economy, consisting of economic activities in connection to purchasing of goods and services. The circumstances of pandemic followed by social distancing led to change in consumer's purchasing

* Email: ankita.chaturvedi@iisuniv.ac.in

**Corresponding author. Email: vaishali.agrawal2412@gmail.com

attitude. Consumers started using online platforms and are deliberately searching for online tools to buy goods or services they want (Dirgantari et al., 2019). Consequently, it leads to rivalry among e-commerce companies.

The corona outbreak in India has converted electronic shopping the preference of many people to buy things. According to a report by Global Web Index, the online trading activity using the internet in India has maximum usage of e-commerce among many countries in the world, along with 59% of internet users between the age of 16 to 64 who say they expect to shop online more frequently even after the pandemic ends. In addition, on 25 March 2020, Big basket an online grocery store had the message “We will be back soon! We are currently experiencing unprecedented demand.” Amazon- a leading e-commerce company has announced on its site that the consumers are relying on them like never before. This hike in B2C e-commerce in India is because of increasing online consumers. However, there are two more segments apart from the one that regularly purchases online. One segment did not purchase online but due to coronavirus forced to start online shopping while the other segment consists of people that up till now either ignorant regarding online shopping or did not have any device for the same. Therefore, it would be interesting to know how many people switch from offline to online mode of shopping before, during, or after COVID-19 times.

2. Review of Literature

Bhatti et al. (2020) has attempted to determine the trends of e-commerce in the duration of COVID-19 globally along with how forthcoming progress in e-commerce industry affect the behavior of consumer in future. The results concluded that there is a significant impact of COVID-19 on e-commerce of the world along with negative in some cases. Coronavirus forced people to make a habit of using the internet in their daily routine. Elrhim and Elsayed (2020) investigated the impact of COVID-19 on the top five e-commerce companies in the world which were selected based on their market value and revenues. The chosen companies were Amazon, Alibaba, Rakuten, Zalando, and ASOS. Coronavirus has been measured based on cumulative infections, cumulative deaths, new coronavirus cases, and new coronavirus deaths on daily basis from 15 March 2020 to 25 May 2020. In addition, the dependent variable was the daily returns of the shares of selected five e-commerce companies. Further, after applying the Beta Standardized Coefficients test, results indicated that total deaths had a high degree of impact on dependent variable followed by total cases and new cases. Han et al. (2020) identified the impact of COVID-19 on the sale of Alibaba’s electronic commerce platform. Further, to find the impact, the researcher applied a fixed-effect model. Results showed a systematic downfall of 22% in the sales of electronic commerce during the outbreak of COVID-19.

While, in post-outbreak duration, the researcher found a significant hike of 11%-26% in sales, which indicates an expansion of online sellers in long run.

Almeida et al. (2020) has analyzed the effect of digital conversion processes in broad three business fields: marketing and sales, labor and social relations, and technology. The effect of digitalization was expected to enhance the development of new digital products and services based on the flexibility principle. Moreover, demand for new talent will increase because of new and different ways of working. In addition, privacy and cybersecurity will emerge as the two important elements, which will assist the integrated development of the internet. Shahzadet al. (2020) examined the difference between female and male electronic learning portals accessibility as per the perspective of students. Partial LM-SEM was used to analyze the empirical data of 280 students from various Malaysian universities. Consequently, the results revealed that females and males have different parameters of usage of electronic learning portals in universities of Malaysia.

Hasan et al. (2020) tried to identify the impact of coronavirus on the e-commerce of Malaysia. The researcher conducted a survey to reach a better outcome. The findings illustrated that due to the maximum import of products from China and the maximum industries are lockdown, it affected the online business of Malaysia drastically. Shahzad et al. (2020) have done the study to identify the impact of COVID-19 on the usage of e-commerce in the healthcare industry of Malaysia by using the Technological, Organizational, and Environmental (TOE) model. Data was collected from the sample of 100 healthcare providers and analysis was done by using SPSS 25 and PLS-SEM 3.0. The findings revealed that e-commerce knowledge, supply chain integration, and organization readiness have a positive significant impact. Richards and Rickard (2020) studied the impact of COVID-19 on the fruit and vegetable markets of Canada. In long term, there were expected changes in online food buying habits of consumers, constraints on immigrant labor, and tighter restrictions on retailers.

Dirgantari et al. (2020) examined the level of satisfaction and use of e-commerce among the consumers during the period of the pandemic with the approach of the Information System Success Model (ISSM) which was generated through quality information, system quality, and quality service. The researcher collected data from 206 e-commerce consumers by distributing questionnaires. SEM was used for data analysis and results confirmed that there is an impact of information quality, system quality, and quality service on the level of satisfaction and use of e-commerce among consumers. Gao et al. (2020) took an initiative to examine the impact of COVID-19 on the online food purchase behavior of consumers in the short term. The researcher adopted a strategy of the instrumental variable to address the endogeneity issues. Consequently, results reflected

that spread of confirmed coronavirus cases led to an increase in purchasing behavior of online food.

Grashuis et al. (2020) tried to study the fluctuations in the attitude of grocery shoppers under the situations of coronavirus pandemic. For the same purpose, the researcher conducted an online survey to elicit the preferences of consumers related to purchasing methods, minimum order quantity, time windows, and fees. The results concluded that in the situation of increasing COVID-19 spread, consumers mostly prefer to shop online. On the contrary, in case of less spread, consumers are willing to purchase inside the grocery shop. Hashem (2020) studied the change in the behavior of consumers during COVID-19 towards online shopping. Variables taken into consideration were necessity, frequency, product or service availability, price and payment method. An online survey was conducted on the citizens (500) of Jordan to understand their purchasing behavior before and after COVID-19. Results indicated that COVID-19 forced the consumers to change their buying behavior by relying more on e-shopping and online payment methods. The pandemic forced people to work virtually and most of the businesses have done this transformation in a very short duration. Therefore, Kim (2020) explained the growth of e-commerce after the pandemic.

Salem and Nor (2020) took an effort to study around ten factors that affect consumers' behavior to acquire e-commerce during COVID-19 in Saudi Arabia. An online questionnaire was distributed among the users of social media by using the snowball sampling technique. The analysis reflected that risk-taking propensity, PU, received lack of alternatives, and support of government affected significantly the behavior of consumers to acquire e-commerce during the outbreak of COVID-19. Tran (2021) focused to identify the impact of the Perceived Effectiveness of E-commerce Platforms (PEEP) on consumers' perceived monetary benefits in forecasting sustainable consumption. Adopting a PLS technique for analysis on a sample size of 617 online consumers, the study identified a moderating positive impact of pandemic fear on the association among economic benefits, PEEP and sustainable consumption.

By reviewing the literature, it was observed that the majority of the studies are focusing on digital transformation during COVID-19 and they talk about changes in e-commerce during COVID-19. But the future aspect is not taken into consideration. Therefore, this study focuses on how many people switch from offline to online mode of shopping before, during, or after COVID-19 times and what are the consumer's expectations.

This paper is designed to analyze the changes in consumers' perceptions and buying behavior due to the COVID-19 pandemic, to study the relation between the demographic variables (age, qualification), the reasons for consumers shifting from online to offline and to analyze the effect of the reasons to purchase online, reasons for switching

from online to offline purchases, and the consumers' expectation from the new e-commerce industry on the likelihood of consumers to purchase online after COVID-19.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Sample and Data Collection

This research work seeks to determine the effect of COVID-19 on consumers' changing behavior towards e-commerce or online shopping and using various electronic platforms for purchasing items. The proposed research is both exploratory and descriptive. Variables used in the study relied on drivers of consumer behavior change comprising the pre and post COVID-19 purchase behavior, reasons to buy online after COVID-19, change in consumer attitude due to COVID-19, reasons for switching from online to offline purchases, and the consumers expectation from the new e-commerce industry. The study is based on 600 Indian internet buyers across income groups and geographies accessing a good assortment of goods and services, selected on the idea of stratified sampling. For this we have divided India into four zones (strata): East, West, North, South, and primary data has been collected by using a structured questionnaire equally filled in by respondents of each stratum. The study focuses on how the shopping habits of consumers changes in the near and distant future, what are the consumers' expectations from the industry of e-commerce after COVID-19 pandemic.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.1. Reliability Testing

Reliability is mainly associated with assuring the method of data collection leads to consistent results. To check whether the data is reliable or not Cronbach's Alpha technique is used. The result stated that Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.824 which shows a high level of internal reliability of our scale with the specific sample.

4.2. Demographic Profile of Consumers

From the table 1, it is studied that almost 56.2 % of consumers are male and 43.8 % are females. In addition, 44.2% of the consumers are of the age less than 25 years, 25.7 % are between 25-35 years of age and 30.1% of the consumers are above 35 years of age. When asked about their education background 3.8 % of consumers are school pass outs, 36.8 % of consumers are graduate, 31.8 % of consumers are professionally educated and 11 % have other qualifications. The average monthly online purchases of the majority 55.2 % of consumers are less than Rs 5000, 24.3 % of consumers are doing between Rs 5000-Rs 10000 average monthly online purchases, and the rest 20.5 % consumers are doing online purchases of more than Rs 10000.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Consumers

	Frequency	Percentage		Frequency	Percentage
Gender			Education		
Male	337	56.2	School Level	23	3.8
Female	263	43.8	Under Graduate/ Graduate	221	36.8
Age			Post Graduate	191	31.8
Less than 25	265	44.2	Professional	99	16.5
25-35	154	25.7	Others	66	11
35-45	113	18.8	Average monthly online Purchases		
45-55	36	6	Less than 5000	331	55.2
55 and above	32	5.3	5000 – 10000	146	24.3
			10000- 15000	56	9.3
			15000 and above	67	11.2

Source: Primary Data Collected by Authors.

Figure 1: Online Buying Behaviour of Consumers

Source: Primary Data Collected by Authors.

It is observed from the figure1 that before COVID-19, 29.7% of consumers were purchasing fashion accessories online and 28.3 % were purchasing pharmaceuticals health hygiene and cosmetics and personal care online followed by 27% of consumers who were

purchasing media and books (both physical and digital). Since the COVID-19 outbreak, the highest % hike in the online purchasing of digital entertainment, e.g., OTTS, etc. is seen followed by a hike in the online purchase of pharmaceuticals, groceries, media and books, education, and online courses. Whereas travel and tourism, i.e., online hotel booking, flight booking, etc. shows a significant decrease in COVID-19 outbreak. It is also observed that 35.4% of consumers will continue to book flight tickets and hotel bookings after COVID-19. 32.3% of consumers will continue to purchase food and beverages online, 34.1% consumers will continue to purchase ICT in electronic goods online and many of the consumers also like to continue with online purchases after COVID-19 with respect to pharmaceuticals, groceries, fashion accessories and digital entertainment. It is also examined that 32.9 percent of consumers have never purchased any sports and fitness-related products online, 29% consumers were never purchased any education and online courses and 24.5% consumers have never booked any hotels for flights online.

Table 2: Changes in Consumers Perceptions and Buying Behaviour due to COVID-19 Pandemic

	Mean	C.V.
I will prefer to travel after COVID-19	4.008	22.68
I decided to spend my next holiday domestically and not to travel abroad	3.688	27.82
I will buy a medical policy to meet my medical expenditures	4.23	30.40
I prefer to do contactless payments	3.595	29.91
I will buy life or term insurances to secure the future of my family	4.01	33.04
I will cut down on my unwanted expenses and start saving more	3.37	36.45
I will prefer to watch movies with my OTTs subscriptions rather than going to cinema halls	3.538	30.81
I will prefer taking medical consultations online rather than offline	3.705	30.77

Note: N = 600. C.V. = Coefficient of Variation. Source: Primary Data Collected by Authors.

Table 2 shows the changes in consumers' perception and buying behavior due to COVID - 19 pandemic. It is observed that the consumers are more concerned about their unpredictable medical expenditure and the majority of them strongly agree (4.23) to the statement that they will buy a medical policy to meet medical expenditures. The consumers also seem to be more conscious about their family's future and security and agree (4.01) to the statement that they will buy term or life insurance. Just because the people were stuck up in lockdown for a long time, and then after life is not normal, they have to follow the social distancing and wear mask, etc., they are fed up with all these and therefore as shown in the figure-1 many consumers agree (4.008) to the statement that they will prefer to travel after COVID-19. The table 2 also shows that the consumers who agree

to the statement (3.705) will prefer taking medical consultation online rather than offline as online they can consult the specialist of the disease from all over the world and can get the best treatment. Some fear of COVID-19 is also observed in the consumers as they (3.688) agree to the statement that they will spend the next holidays domestically and not travel abroad. The mean of preference to do the online contactless payment is observed as 3.595 which means the consumers have moved to digital payments now after COVID-19. The highest coefficient of variation (36.45) is observed in consumers' responses regarding cutting down the unwanted expenditure and saving more for the future, followed by 3.041 coefficient of variation in the statement that they will buy term or life insurance to secure the future of their family. The least variation is observed in the statement that the consumers will prefer to travel after COVID-19.

Table 3: Consumers Expectations From New E-Commerce Industry

	Weighted Average	Rank Analysis
Wide variety of product and services offerings	4.18	1
Well structured channels	4.03	6
Easy payment options	3.99	9
Fast delivery	4.11	3
Good customer care support	4.01	7
Easy exchange/ returns	4.05	5
Availability of applications/ websites in all major languages	3.98	8
Discounted price	4.08	4
Secure payment gateways	4.15	2

Source: Primary Data Collected by Authors

Table 3 shows the expectations of consumers from the new e-commerce industry after COVID-19. The rank analysis is done based on a weighted average. It is observed that consumers expect a wide variety of product and service offerings and they are also looking forward to a secured payment gateway. The e-commerce industry should also work on faster deliveries and offering products at a discounted price to meet the expectation of consumers. The consumers also look forward to easy exchanges/ returns of the products followed by a good structure/ organized channel so that they can easily search for what they want.

4.3. Correlation Analysis

Before applying Pearson's correlation, all the assumptions regarding the scale of variables, the linear relationship between the variables, outliers in the data, and normality were checked. Correlation analysis reveals that there exist a positive low correlation between

age, educational qualification, and the reasons for switching back from online to offline purchases. Whereas a negative low correlation is observed between age and qualification and the expectation of consumers from the new e-commerce industry. The $p < 0.05$, which signifies that the relationship is significant between all the variables.

Table 4 : Correlation Analysis

	Pearson Correlation	Sig (2 tailed)
Age and the reasons to purchase online.	0.237	0.00
Educational qualification and the reasons to purchase online.	0.174	0.00
Age and the consumers' expectations from the new e-commerce industry.	-0.162	0.00
Educational qualifications and the consumers' expectations from the new e-commerce industry.	-0.135	0.001

Note: N = 600. Source:Results using SPSS Software

4.4. Regression Analysis

Logistic regression was applied to ascertain the impact of reasons to purchase online, reasons for switching from online to offline purchases, and the consumers' expectation from the new e-commerce industry on the likelihood that consumers will continue online purchases after COVID-19.

Table 5: Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	Df	Sig.
Step 1	Step	23.328	3	.000
	Block	23.328	3	.000
	Model	23.328	3	.000

Table 6: Model Summary

Step 1	-2 Log likelihood	Cox and Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
	800.263 ^a	.038	.051

Note: a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 4 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001. Source:Results using SPSS Software.

The model of logistic regression is statistically significant, $\chi^2(3) = 23.328$, $p < 0.0005$. Table 6 of model summary shows the Cox and Snell R Square and Nagelkerke R Square values, which are helpful in calculating the explained variation. Sometimes, these values are called as pseudo R^2 values (and will have lower values than in multiple regression). However, they are explicated in the same way, but with more wariness.

Therefore, on the basis of our model, variation explained in the dependent variable ranges from 3.8 % to 5.1%.

Table 7: Classification Table^a

Observed			Predicted		
			Online purchases after COVID-19		Percentage Correct
			No	Yes	
Step 1	Online purchases after COVID-19.	No	267	68	79.7
		Yes	176	89	33.6
	Overall Percentage				59.3

Note: a. The cut value is .500. Source: Results using SPSS Software.

The classification in the table 7 shows the percentage accuracy in classification which is 59.3 %.It is analyzed from the table that reasons to purchase online (p= 0.000), reasons for switching from online to offline purchases (p = 0.004) added significantly to the model/prediction, but the consumers’ expectation from the new e-commerce industry (p= 0.398)did not add significantly to the model. Therefore, it can be concluded that increasing reasons to purchase online have a positive association with the increased online purchases after COVID-19 but increasing reasons to switch from online to offline purchase is associated with a reduction in online purchases after COVID-19.

Table 8: Variables in the Equation

		B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 1a	Reasons to purchase online	.561	.149	14.285	1	.000	1.753
	Reasons for switching from online to offline purchases	-.280	.098	8.101	1	.004	.756
	The consumers expectation from the new e-commerce industry	.114	.135	.715	1	.398	1.121
	Constant	-1.946	.823	5.593	1	.018	.143

Note: a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: reasons to purchase online reasons for switching from online to offline purchases , expectation from the new e-commerce industry Source: Results using SPSS Software.

5. Findings

COVID-19 is greater than a world health emergency along with a worldwide financial crisis, which could transcend the global financial crisis, happened in 2008-09 (Loayza and Pennings, 2020). Focusing on a current online survey merged with national-level data, this research paper identifies the effect of COVID-19 on customers’ changing behavior

towards e-commerce or online shopping and using various electronic platforms for purchasing items. To address the issues, researchers collected the data of 600 Indian internet buyers across income groups and geographies accessing a good assortment of goods and services, selected on the idea of stratified sampling. For this, researchers have divided India into four zones (strata): East, West, North, South, and primary data have been collected by using a structured questionnaire equally filled in by respondents of each stratum.

During this COVID-19 pandemic, consumers have tried their best to adapt to strange times without a lot of footholds and shifting their behavior as a result. The finding of this study resulted in showing that the majority of the consumers will like to use online shops and physical stores equally once the COVID-19 pandemic is over. Many of the consumers want to switch back from online to offline purchases because of no same-day delivery in online purchases. Further, security and privacy concern, lack of knowledge of the online transaction and lack of access to online payment mechanism is also a matter of great concern for the consumers. Although, with the increase in mobile towers these days, the digital connectivity is not much concern for switching from online to offline purchases. In addition, language of the applications is also not found a major barrier in online purchases. Moreover, consumers are more concerned about their unpredictable medical expenditures and they will prefer to buy a medical policy to meet medical expenditures or the term plans or insurance to secure the future of their family. Just because the people were stuck up in lockdown for a long time, and then the afterlife is not normal, they have to follow the social distancing and wear a mask, etc., they are fed up with all these and therefore will prefer to do domestic travel after COVID-19. Consumers expect a wide variety of product and service offerings and they are also looking forward to a secured payment gateway. The e-commerce industry should also work on faster deliveries and offering products at a discounted price to meet the expectation of consumers. The consumers also look forward to easy exchanges/ returns of the products followed by a good structure/organized channel so that they can easily search for what they want.

A positive low correlation is observed between age, educational qualification, and the reasons for switching back from online to offline purchases. Whereas a negative low correlation is observed between age and qualification of and the expectation of consumers from the new e-commerce industry. Logistic regression was applied to ascertain the impact of reasons to purchase online, reasons for switching from online to offline purchases, and the consumers' expectation from the new e-commerce industry on the likelihood that consumers will continue online purchases after COVID-19. It is found that expectation from the new e-commerce industry did not add significantly to the model, and increasing reasons to purchase online have a positive association with the increased

online purchases after COVID-19 but increasing reasons to switch from online to offline purchase is associated with a reduction in online purchases after COVID-19.

6. Conclusion

The purview of e-business is as large as an ocean and therefore there is lot of implementation hurdles. When one considers of the e-business, even after the main objective stays identical as of any traditional business, how they work to enhance the performance is different (Chaturvedi and Joshi, 2019). Based on the results, this research showed that people are more inclined towards online shopping during and after COVID-19. Government regulations and support should emphasize the hygiene of food sold on online sites. Moreover, the people who are not able to buy food and other products online due to their technical glitches (e.g., unstable or unavailability of the internet, non-familiarity with smartphones, language issues) also seek attention from government and e-commerce companies. Further, e-commerce companies must handle their system of delivery in a better way and try to shorten the time period of pick up and delivery. Also, e-commerce companies should enhance the capacity of managing the temporary rise in demand by employing more labor and capital resources. Companies are required to create powerful marketing strategies to keep a hold in the sectors.

There is a limitation to this study. This work has been conducted in India, so the possibility of results application for other countries is uncertain. It is suggested to examine the impact of COVID-19 in other countries. Further studies can make in-depth sector-wise comparisons considering the increase in revenue generation to e-commerce companies post COVID-19.

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